

Maria J. Santofimia, Henry Llumiguano, Javier Dorado, Ángel Jesús Sáez, Vicente Díaz, and Álvaro Carrera (2024): MIRATAR: A Smart Mirror Solution for Remote Health Monitoring and Rehabilitation in Older Adults. In: Proceedings of the Joint visuAAL-GoodBrother Conference on trustworthy video- and audio-based assistive technologies – COST Action CA19121 - Network on Privacy-Aware Audio- and Video-Based Applications for Active and Assisted Living

MIRATAR: A Smart Mirror Solution for Remote Health Monitoring and Rehabilitation in Older Adults

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Abstract

The MIRATAR project focuses on advancing the digital transformation of the care economy by leveraging innovative technologies such as a smart mirror and a virtual caregiver to address the frailty and multimorbidity challenges faced by older adults. By adopting a 4P approach (Predictive, Preventive, Personalized, and Participatory care), the project aims to empower individuals to manage their health proactively at home. With real-time data collection and AI-driven interventions, the system supports health literacy, behaviour change, and comprehensive care. This platform targets the challenges of promoting self-management, reducing institutionalisation, and improving quality of life for older adults.

Introduction

The demographic shift towards an ageing population presents unique challenges to modern healthcare systems, particularly in the management of frailty and multimorbidity. Frailty, characterized by diminished strength and endurance, increases vulnerability to adverse health outcomes, while multimorbidity, defined as the presence of two or more chronic conditions, complicates patient care due to complex treatment protocols and the risk of polypharmacy. Addressing these conditions requires a transformative approach in how care is delivered, moving from the current disease-centred model to a person-centred paradigm.

At the core of the project is the development of a smart mirror system, which leverages artificial intelligence (AI) and internet of things (IoT) technologies to create a personalised and interactive healthcare environment. This system includes a virtual caregiver, designed to support individuals in managing their frailty and multimorbidity through tailored interventions, health literacy initiatives, and behaviour change strategies. By placing the patient at the centre of the healthcare process, MIRATAR aligns with the broader objective of creating a digital, less institutionalised care economy.

The contributions of this work are outlined as follows: 1) Empowerment of individuals to self-manage frailty and multimorbidity risks through personalised self-management strategies, supported by multimodal and technology-based interventions; 2) Development of AI-based prediction models for frailty and multimorbidity risks, which will enable the delivery of personalised interventions, and the prediction of future health risks based on individualised data; 3) Integration of innovative ICT solutions into the care ecosystem, creating a cyber-physical platform that supports risk management and health monitoring; 4) Evaluation of the impact of these technologies on patient well-being, including the emotional and psychological aspects of care, with a specific focus on gender differences and public health policy recommendations; 6) Recommendations for public authorities, focusing on organisational and social changes needed to adopt and scale these technologies within healthcare systems.

The rise of digital health technologies, including wearable devices, virtual assistants, and AI-driven health platforms, has the potential to revolutionise chronic disease management and preventive care. While commercial products such as Fitbit, Apple Watch, and Google Fit have made strides in encouraging healthier lifestyles, their impact on frailty and multimorbidity populations remains underexplored. A systematic review has found that although wearable devices may increase motivation for physical activity, there is little evidence to suggest they significantly improve health outcomes in individuals with chronic conditions as stated in Burbach et al. (2019). Furthermore, AI and machine learning models have gained traction in healthcare, with applications in disease prediction, risk assessment, and decision support systems. However, these technologies face

barriers to adoption, primarily due to the lack of integration into clinical workflows and issues of interoperability as stated in Jo et al. (2019). To overcome these limitations, MIRATAR focuses on its innovative smart mirror solution, which serves as an interactive platform for real-time health monitoring and personalised care interventions. The smart mirror integrates AI-driven predictive models and IoT technologies, allowing older adults to manage their frailty and multimorbidity at home. This system acts as a virtual caregiver, delivering tailored health advice and tracking key health metrics, while also fostering engagement through user-friendly, non-intrusive interactions.

Conclusions

The MIRATAR project offers an innovative solution for addressing the complex challenges of frailty and multimorbidity in older adults. Through its smart mirror system and virtual caregiver, the platform enables personalised, AI-driven interventions that promote self-management, health literacy, and proactive care.

Acknowledgments

This paper is funded by MCIN/ AEI /10.13039/501100011033 under Grant TALENT-BELIEF (PID2020-116417RB-C44) and the Project MIRATAR TED2021-132149B-C41 funded by MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by the European Union NextGenerationEU/PRTR.

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